

Structural Studies on Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II), Cu(II), Mn(II), Fe(III), Cr(III) and VO(II) Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthaldehyde Semicarbazone

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Manuscript received 30 September 1982, revised 21 April 1983, accepted 19 July 1983

The chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde semicarbazone (Hnsc) of the type $M(\text{nsc})$, $[M = \text{Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II)}]$; $M(\text{nsc})_2\text{Cl}$ $[M = \text{Fe(III), Cr(III)}]$; $M(\text{nsc})\text{Cl}\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ $[M = \text{Cu(II)}]$ and $M(\text{nsc})\text{Cl}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ $[M = \text{Mn(II), VO(II)}]$ have been isolated and characterised on the basis of their elemental analyses, conductance, ir, electronic and magnetic studies. Various ligand field parameters have been evaluated for Ni(II), Co(II), Cr(III) and VO(II) chelates. All these chelates have octahedral structure.

THE present report describes the isolation of chelates of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde semicarbazone (Hnsc) with Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(II), Cu(II), Mn(II), Fe(III), Cr(III) and VO(II). Their probable structures have been determined on the basis of their elemental analyses, magnetic, conductivity, electronic and infrared measurements. Only isolation of silicon(IV) derivative of semicarbazone and thio-semicarbazone is reported in literature¹.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Metal chlorides were used in the preparation of metal chelate of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Fe(III), Cr(III), Mn(II) and VO(II). Ferrous ammonium sulphate was used to prepare Fe(II) chelate.

The ligand was prepared by refluxing (1 hr) ethanolic solution of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and aqueous solution of semicarbazone hydrochloride in 1:1 mole ratio in presence of sodium acetate. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

All complexes were prepared by refluxing the required quantities of ligand in DMF and aqueous solution of metal salt in presence of 1.0 g of sodium acetate. The separated solid was filtered, washed with ethanol, DMF and finally with ether, and dried.

Magnetic susceptibilities were measured on standard Guoy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as the calibrant. Visible reflectance spectra were measured on VSU-2P spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded in KBr on Spectromom-2000 spectrophotometer. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen in the complexes were deter-

mined by micro-analytical methods. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 by Carius method². Chloride was also determined by Carius method. Metal in each compound was estimated by titrating against standard EDTA after decomposing the complex and also by gravimetric oxide method. The conductivities of the complexes in DMF were measured using Toshniwal conductometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and conductivity data are presented in Table 1. Molar conductivities (in DMF) of Cr(III) and Fe(III) chelates suggest their 1:1 electrolyte nature while the rest of the complexes are non-electrolytes.

The infrared spectral data are given in Table 2. The sharp band at 3260 cm^{-1} in the ligand assignable to phenolic OH (hydrogen bonded) stretching frequency¹ disappears in the Ni(II), Co(II), Cr(III), Fe(II) and Fe(III) complexes showing deprotonation of metal ions. The ligand also shows strong band at 1280 cm^{-1} which may be attributed to the phenolic ν_{CO} vibration. A shift of this band to higher frequency ($\sim 1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the complexes indicates chelation of ligand to the metal atom through phenolic oxygen. The presence of a band near 3240 cm^{-1} in Cu(II), Mn(II) and VO(II) complexes may be due to ν_{OH} of water molecules associated with the complexes. This is further justified by the presence of a band around 1600 cm^{-1} as deformation band of water molecules.

The sharp band at 1590 cm^{-1} in the ligand due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ of Schiff's base residue shifts to lower frequencies at $\sim 1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes showing

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, MAGNETIC and CONDUCTIVITY DATA

Compound	Analysis %; Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} (B.M.) Obs./ (Calcd.)	Molar conductance ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹
	M	C	H	N	Cl		
[Cu(nsc)Cl.2H ₂ O]	17.16 (17.50)	39.12 (39.67)	2.41 (2.75)	10.90 (11.57)	9.30 (9.78)	1.78	12.2
[Ni(nsc) ₂]	11.25 (11.45)	55.78 (56.17)	3.16 (3.51)	15.95 (16.38)	—	2.94 (3.16)	8.6
[Co(nsc) ₂]	11.35 (11.49)	55.85 (56.15)	3.23 (3.50)	15.90 (16.36)	—	4.1	14.8
[Fe(nsc) ₂]Cl	10.09 (10.24)	52.10 (52.81)	3.05 (3.30)	15.13 (15.50)	6.25 (6.51)	5.90	70.3
[Fe(nsc) ₂]	10.80 (10.95)	56.07 (56.48)	3.18 (3.53)	16.19 (16.46)	—	5.3	11.4
[Cr(nsc) ₂]Cl	9.45 (9.60)	52.88 (53.18)	3.08 (3.32)	15.16 (15.50)	6.22 (6.55)	3.83 (3.92)	68.5
[Mn(nsc)Cl.H ₂ O]	15.90 (16.18)	42.60 (42.87)	3.26 (3.57)	12.28 (12.50)	—	1.06	13.4
[VO(nsc)Cl.H ₂ O]	14.51 (14.62)	41.06 (41.32)	3.29 (3.44)	11.92 (12.05)	—	0.814	17.2

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹)

Compound	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{C=N}$	$\nu_{C=O}$ (phenolic)
[H-nsc]	3260 s, m	1660 s, s	1590 s, s	1280 s, s
[Cu(nsc)Cl.2H ₂ O]	3230 s, m	1650 s, s	1560 s, s	1810 s, s
[Ni(nsc) ₂]	—	1640 br	1580 s, br	1300 s, s
[Co(nsc) ₂]	—	1640 s, br	1585 s, br	1310 s, s
[Fe(nsc) ₂]Cl	—	1630 s, m	1560 s, s	1310 s, m
[Fe(nsc) ₂]	—	1610 s, m	1580 s, s	1320 s, s
[Cr(nsc) ₂]Cl	—	1630 s, s	1580 s, s	1290 s, s
[Mn(nsc)Cl.H ₂ O]	3220 m	1630 s, m	1570 m	1310 s, s
[VO(nsc)Cl.H ₂ O]	3240 s, m	1630 s, s	1560 s, s	1310 s, s

s, m=sharp, medium, s, s=sharp, strong, br=broad, s, br=sharp, broad, m=medium.

coordination through the nitrogen atom³. The ligand band at 1660 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ and shows downward shifting in metal complexes, indicating participation of this group in coordination⁴.

The ligand shows band at 3160 cm⁻¹ which may be due to ν_{NH} but this band remains unaltered in the complexes indicating nonparticipation of this group in coordination.

This infrared data suggest that Hnsc behaves as tridentate chelating agent for the metal ions, coordinating through phenolic oxygen, nitrogen atom of C=N group and ketonic oxygen.

Visible reflectance spectra of Cu(II) complex shows a broad band in 13750-15000 cm⁻¹ due to ${}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. The broadness of band and its position indicate distorted octahedral stereochemistry for this complex. The room temperature magnetic moment of the complex (Table 1) is very close to spin only value of Cu(II) complex⁵.

Ni(II) complex shows four bands in their reflectance spectra favouring an octahedral stereochemistry⁶. Out of these four bands, three can be assigned to spin allowed d-d transition, 11240, 16000 and 24691 cm⁻¹, assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. The fourth band at 10752 cm⁻¹ is probably

spin forbidden⁷ and may be assigned to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ transition.

The observed spin allowed bands have been utilised to obtain ligand field parameters (Table 3). The lower value of B_{35} is considered to be indicative of a greater covalent character in metal ligand bond⁸, and the complex shows ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.39) in the range required for Oh complex. The ν_1 band shows splitting into two bands suggesting the presence of low symmetry component. These are assigned in D_{4h} symmetry as transition to the ${}^3B_{2g}$ and 3E_g (components of ${}^3T_{2g}$ in Oh) level and have energies of $10 Dq^{XY}$ and $10 Dq^{XY} - 35/4 Dt$, respectively. Therefore the amount of splitting in ν_1 band can be taken as the degree of distortion⁹ and Dt (55 cm⁻¹) can be calculated. Using $Dt(D_{4h})$ and Dq^{XY} (1124 cm⁻¹), the Dq^Z (1028 cm⁻¹) was calculated. The low value of Dq^Z suggests that the field strength is lower compared to inplanar field strength. The experimental room temperature μ_{eff} value (Table 1) lies in the range required for octahedral stereochemistry and is in good agreement with the values calculated by substitution of the experimental $10 Dq$ and λ_0 value (-315 cm⁻¹) in relationship⁹

$$\mu_{eff} = \mu_{cal} \left(1 - 4 \lambda_0 / 10 Dq \right)^{s.o.}$$

The room temperature magnetic moment of Co(II) complex (Table 1) is lower than that expected for octahedral complex. In absence of low temperature magnetic moment, it is rather difficult to discuss the significance of this difference. The diffuse reflectance spectra of Co(II) complex give three d-d transition bands at 9803, 19607 and 22727 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. The spin allowed transition energies have been used to calculate $10 Dq$ and B_{35} (Table 3). The ν_2/ν_1 ratio 2.00 comes very close to the ratio required for an octahedral structure¹⁰.

The reflectance spectra of Fe(III) complex shows three bands and may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (14710 cm⁻¹), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (19040 cm⁻¹) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow$

TABLE 3—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED TRANSITION ENERGIES IN cm^{-1} FOR THE Ni(II), Co(II) AND Cr(III) COMPLEXES

Compound	Method of calculation	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	B_{ss}	β_{ss}	$\delta\nu$	10 Dq	λ	ν_3/ν_1
Ni(nse) ₂	Expt	11240	16000	24691	—	—	—	—	—	1.42
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	24777	485	0.47	+86	11240	—	—
	(b)	10 Dq	15679	Fitted	442	0.43	-321	11240	-51.62	—
	(c)	10 Dq	15843	24837	464	0.45	—	11240	—	—
Co(nse) ₂	Expt	9803	19607	22727	—	—	—	—	—	2.00
	(a)	Fitted	18840	Fitted	1067	0.95	-767	12884	—	—
	(b)	9971	Fitted	Fitted	962	0.86	+168	10306	—	—
	(c)	8629	18432	20363	861	0.77	—	9804	—	—
Cr(nse) ₂ Cl	Expt	17290	22730	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	(a)	10 Dq	Fitted	36820	512	0.56	—	17290	—	—
	(b)	10 Dq	22727	Fitted	511.8	0.56	-3	17290	42.80	—
	(c)	10 Dq	22730	36820	512	0.56	0	17290	—	—
	(d)	10 Dq	22734	36824	512.6	0.56	+4	17290	—	—

* Equations used in method a, b, c are given in the appendix.

4E_g (25000 cm^{-1}) transitions assuming idealized octahedral symmetry¹¹. The magnetic moment (Table 1) of Fe(III) complex under study also supports octahedral stereochemistry¹².

A band observed in the spectrum of Fe(II) complex at 11500 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $^6T_{2g} \rightarrow ^6E_g$ transition, characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry around metal ion⁶. The room temperature magnetic moment of Fe(II) complex (5.5 B.M.) is consistent with spin free octahedral geometry around metal ion¹³.

The reflectance spectra of Cr(III) complex show bands at 17290 and 22730 cm^{-1} which are assigned to $^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and $^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) d-d transitions in octahedral stereochemistry¹⁴. The low energy band at 11111 cm^{-1} may be due to $^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ spin forbidden transition. The higher energy spin allowed ν_3 transition band, $^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$, usually occurs above 30000 cm^{-1} which would have been obscured because of ligand absorption in this region⁶. These spin allowed transitions are utilised to compute important ligand field parameters (Table 3).

The values of B_{ss} and β_{ss} are found to be 653 and 0.71, respectively. The less than unity β_{ss} value suggests π type of interpretation between metal and ligand. The low value of β_{ss} (0.56) is believed to be indicative of both π and σ type delocalization¹⁵. An attempt have been made to calculate covalency parameter¹⁶, ratio of the oscillator strength¹⁷, the spin orbit coupling parameter¹⁸ (λ) and the values are found to be 0.78, 2.58×10^{-2} , 42.80, respectively. The value of ratio of the oscillator strength is in fair agreement with oscillator strength ratio of spin forbidden (Laporte-forbidden) to spin allowed (Laporte-forbidden) with intensity stealing. The room temperature μ_{eff} value (Table 1) falls in the range required for octahedral stereochemistry¹⁹ and is in good agreement with the calculated value⁹.

Mn(II) complex exhibits bands at 11910, 16660, 23810 cm^{-1} indicating penta or hexacoordinated structure²⁰. The Mn(II) complex shows subnormal

magnetic moment (Table 1) which may be due to metal-metal interaction²¹. This suggests that the complex may have binuclear structure.

The room temperature magnetic moment value of the VO(II) complex (0.31 B.M.) is abnormally lower than the spin only value of 1.73 B.M. This abnormal value may be due to the presence of exchanged coupled antiferromagnetism²². The VO(II) complex under study exhibits three bands, 12220, 15630 and 22730 cm^{-1} , at room temperature, which may be assigned to $eg \rightarrow b_{2g}$, $eg \rightarrow a_{1g}$ and $eg \rightarrow b_{1g}$ transitions, respectively. These transitions are based on Oh symmetry with tetragonal distortion, elongation being along Z axis. Attempts have been made to calculate the values of radial parameters Ds, Dt, Dq^{xy} which are found to be 2760, -788 and 1051 cm^{-1} , respectively. The negative value of Dt suggest weak σ donating ability but still more than π donating ability since Dq and Ds both are positive.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Prof. M. M. Kulkarni, Head of the Chemistry Department for the facilities and thankful to Principal, Pratap College, Amalner, for kind help.

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APPENDIX

Equations used in band fitting calculations.

Metal - Ni(II) and Cr(III)

Method :

$$(a) B = \frac{2\nu_1^2 + \nu_2^2 - 3\nu_1\nu_2}{15\nu_2 - 27\nu_1}$$

$$(b) B = \frac{2\nu_1^2 + \nu_2^2 - 3\nu_1\nu_2}{15\nu_2 - 27\nu_1}$$

$$(c) B = \frac{\nu_2 + \nu_1 - 3\nu_1}{15}$$

$$(d) B = \frac{1}{15} [3\nu_1 \pm \{25(\nu_2 - \nu_1)^2 - 16\nu_1^2\}^{\frac{1}{2}}]$$

$$\nu_{2,3} = \frac{1}{3}(15B + 80 Dq) \pm \frac{1}{3}[(15B - 10 Dq)^2 + 120 Dq.B]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Metal - Co(II)

$$(a) B = \frac{1}{30} [-(2\nu_1 - \nu_2) \pm \{ \nu_1^2 + \nu_2^2 + \nu_1\nu_2 \}^{\frac{1}{2}}]$$

$$10 Dq = 2\nu_1 - \nu_2 + 15B$$

$$(b) B = \frac{1}{30} [7(\nu_2 - 2\nu_1) \pm \{81\nu_2^2 - 16\nu_1(\nu_2 - \nu_1)\}^{\frac{1}{2}}]$$

$$10 Dq = \frac{1}{3}(2\nu_2 - \nu_1) + 5B$$

$$(c) B = \frac{\nu_2 + \nu_1 - 3\nu_1}{15}$$

$$10 Dq = \nu_2 - \nu_1$$

$$\nu_1 = \frac{1}{3}(10 Dq - 15B) + \frac{1}{3}[(10 Dq + 15B)^2 - 120 Dq.B]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\nu_2 = \frac{1}{3}(30 Dq - 15B) + \frac{1}{3}[(10 Dq + 15B)^2 - 120 Dq.B]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\nu_3 = [(10 Dq + 15B)^2 - 120 Dq.B]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$